

Registration of EOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EOSC EU Node

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Abstract The *EOSC EU Node (EEN) Resource Catalogue* is designed to offer discovery and access to the map of resources made available in the EOSC Federation via the EOSC Nodes, including the EEN itself. In particular, it aggregates research product profiles (publications, research data, research software) collected from the research product catalogues of EOSC Nodes. The resulting Catalogue is accessible via the *EOSC Resource Hub* discovery portal (and open APIs), and can be used to discover, access, and monitor EOSC research products across the EOSC Nodes in the Federation.

This document outlines the EOSC Resource Catalogue interoperability guidelines that EOSC Node Research Product Catalogue providers should follow to register their catalogues with the EEN Resource Catalogue, making their research products discoverable, visible, and accessible beyond their Node's boundaries.

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The EOSC EU Node Resource Catalogue

The *EOSC EU Node Resource Catalogue* (*EEN Resource Catalogue*, also known as the *EOSC Knowledge Graph*) is an indexed collection of metadata profiles that describe *EOSC Resources*. Such profiles are collected from a list of trusted sources and are today searchable and accessible via the [EOSC Resource Hub discovery portal](https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources) shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - EOSC Resource Hub discovery portal (<https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources>).

Figure 2 - EEN Resource Catalogue data model.

The purpose of the EEN Catalogue is to offer to users and machines (via APIs) a single discovery entry-point to all resources made available by EOSC Nodes (including the EEN itself) through the EOSC Federation. Its resource data model is shown in Figure 2. All resources in the catalogue have at least one Contributor (an organization that provides or operates the resource) and are offered via at least one EOSC Node, which could be the EEN or one of the candidate Nodes in the build-up phase. An EOSC Node has one responsible Contributor, namely the legal entity organization entitled to its governance.

Figure 3 - EOSC Node Research Product Catalogues: onboarding data sources (blue cylinders) and research products (red circles) from EOSC Nodes (light blue rectangles)

This document focuses on the processes and interoperability guidelines that developers of EOSC Node research product catalogues must follow and implement to register and federate in the EEN Resource Catalogue two kinds of resources:

- **Research Product Catalogues** of EOSC Nodes: An EOSC Node Research Product Catalogue is an **EEN data source** that offers discovery and access to research products. As shown in Figure 3, by catalogue the EEN considers:
 - **Repositories:** services that offer publishing functionality (e.g., deposition, preservation, discovery, access), such as data repositories, software repositories, institutional repositories, or catch-all repositories; for example, [CERN Open Data Portal](https://openaire.eu), and [Zenodo.org](https://zenodo.org) are repository-type research product catalogues for the EOSC CERN Node;
 - **Aggregators:** services populating a catalogue of research product profiles by aggregating (harvesting, harmonizing, and indexing) profiles from a set of repositories (or other aggregators), such as repositories and aggregators, operated within the context of EOSC Nodes to share, discover, and access research products; for example, research.fi is an aggregator-type research product catalogue for the EOSC Finnish Node.
- **Research products** (publications, research data, research software, and other products)

hosted by a data source: research products are the final results of scientific experiments, of the kind scientists would report on their curriculum; typically deposited into repositories by scientists, and including bibliographic metadata for discovery (e.g., title, abstract, keywords, publishing date) and attribution (e.g., funder, grant, author, and organization names and PIDs) and a set of files.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the EEN Resource Catalogue also includes research products from EEN “backbone” data sources. These are data sources considered relevant for the population of a map of research products that complements the ones shared by EOSC Node catalogues, to include interlinked resources (e.g., links to data and software products), and resources of potential interest to EOSC Nodes, but not available in their catalogues. The list of backbone data sources, prescribed by the European Commission LOT1 tender, includes the [OpenAIRE Graph](#), [SoftwareHeritage](#), [European Data Portal](#), [CORDIS](#), and other EC-operated data sources.

An EOSC Node can offer more than one research product catalogue. Once a catalogue is registered and validated, research product metadata records are aggregated from it into the EOSC Resource Catalogue and will include provenance information about (relationships to the identifier of):

- The **data source** metadata record from which their records were harvested;
- The **EOSC Node** metadata record to which the data source is affiliated.

Note that the same product can be harvested from multiple data sources, hence be associated with multiple EOSC Nodes.

Integrating Research Product Catalogues in the EEN Resource Catalogue

This document describes the EEN interoperability guidelines and tools that Contributors of EOSC Nodes must implement to share their catalogues and research product metadata records via the EEN Resource Catalogue, thereby enabling discovery and monitoring of resources across Nodes in the EOSC Federation. To this aim, as illustrated in Figure 3, EOSC Contributors, responsible for the Node catalogues, will:

- **Make their catalogue compliant** with the [EOSC Interoperability Guidelines for EOSC data sources](#);
- **Register the catalogues** in the EEN Resource Catalogue;
- **Validate the catalogues** to verify technical compliance with the Guidelines.

The EEN Resource Catalogue will:

- **Aggregate** (harvest, harmonize, and index) research product metadata records from the catalogues on regular intervals;
- **Filter** the aggregated records based on a set of **quality criteria**, aiming at excluding records lacking “relevant” metadata information and non-scientific products (e.g., sales, explicit content).

In the following sections, such steps are described in detail.

Compliance of EOSC Research Product Catalogues with EEN Interoperability Guidelines

To comply with the EEN Resource Catalogue interoperability guidelines, Research Product catalogues must implement the following interoperability guidelines:

- Implement the [OAI-PMH protocol](#) APIs as described in **Appendix A**;
- Expose their metadata records complying with the DataCite application profile in **Appendix B**, i.e., DataCite with specific formats and vocabularies.

If an EOSC Node Resource Catalogue is operated and maintained by the OpenAIRE Graph (for example, as in the [Netherlands Research Portal](#)), its sources are inherently compliant with these interoperability guidelines. Consequently, such catalogues are automatically integrated into the EEN Resource Catalogue via the OpenAIRE Graph. Registration of the Catalogue to the EEN Contribution Dashboard is still necessary to claim its association with the EOSC Node.

Registration of EOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EEN Resource Catalogue

The Contributor initiates the EEN Contributor's Dashboard self-service for enrolling the **EOSC Node** and the onboarding of research product catalogue(s) as a **data source**. Detailed instructions are provided in the **Appendix C** of this document.

Validation of EOSC Research Product Catalogues

Once the research product catalogue has been registered in the EEN Contributor Dashboard, the EEN Resource Catalogue activates the process of validation of research product metadata records. The EEN Resource Catalogue team will validate compliance to the interoperability guidelines and contact the Contributor in case the validation of protocol implementation or metadata structure and semantics fails. Further rounds of validation will follow, until compatibility is reached and the research products are onboarded into the EEN Catalogue.

EEN Resource Catalogue quality criteria

The EEN Resource Catalogue collects metadata records of research products from backbone data sources and from EOSC Node catalogues that are compatible with the EEN interoperability guidelines above.

At this stage, a further step of quality check and filtering is applied to ensure that the EEN Resource Catalogue only contains research products whose metadata records meet expected minimum quality criteria. Such criteria, which may be updated in the future to reflect different restrictions, currently consist of a set of “minimum metadata completion” criteria, which vary by research product resource type:

- **All products** should have at least one PID from the following eligible schemas: DOI, ArXiv, PubMed, Handle, SoftwareHeritageID, PDBs, ENAs, UNIPROT;

- **Publication products:** *titles, creators/authors, abstract/description, publishing date* are mandatory properties;
- **Research data products:** *titles, creators/authors, publishing date* are mandatory properties;
- **Research software products:** *titles, publishing date* are mandatory properties.

The current quality criteria have been identified by analyzing the degree of completeness of metadata records in the OpenAIRE Graph, which collects content from 140,000 sources at the global level, and identifying the minimal set of mandatory fields that would not exclude a large percentage of products by resource type. Hence, they should not be regarded as finalized, but indicative of the methodology and opportunities for improvement the EEN could undertake in the future. Criteria can and will change in the future, taking into consideration other aspects such as FAIRness of metadata and content, intended usage, etc. agreed upon by the European Commission in order to meet community demands.

Appendix A: Use of OAI-PMH

The usage of one of the major protocols, [OAI-PMH v2.0 protocol](#), in the context of these Guidelines and its application profile is described below.

Metadata Format

Metadata must be encoded following the metadata format defined in the OpenAIRE Application Profile. The recommended metadataPrefix is oai_openaire. For information on how to use the individual properties, please refer to the section [Application Profile Overview](#).

Harvesting Batch_Size

The common convention for the harvesting batch_size via OAI-PMH is '100' records per request [[Open Archives - OAI Flow Control](#)]. If more records are available beyond that first page with batch_size records, a "resumptionToken" is presented. The recommendation is to have a batch_size between 100 and 500 records per request.

Compatibility of Aggregators

Aggregators (e.g., on the national or thematic level) must follow the same instructions and add, at the metadata record level, provenance information on the original data source harvested by the aggregator. Following the [OAI-PMH protocol provenance guidelines](#), the provenance information has to be provided in the <about> node element of an OAI record, as displayed in the following example:

```
<about>
  <provenance xmlns="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance"
    xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
    xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance
    http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/provenance.xsd">
    <originDescription altered="true" harvestDate="2012-09-17T14:58:36Z">
      <baseURL>http://dspace.library.uu.nl:8080/dspace-oai/request</baseURL>
      <identifier>oai:dspace.library.uu.nl:1874/218065</identifier>
      <timestamp>2012-01-19T12:38:56Z</timestamp>
      <metadataNamespace>
        http://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/oai_dc/
      </metadataNamespace>
      <repositoryId>opendoar:98765</repositoryId>
      <repositoryName>DSpace Library</repositoryName>
    </originDescription>
  </provenance>
</about>
```

The *originDescription* element is added to the metadata record by the aggregator and contains the following elements (taken from <https://www.openarchives.org/OAI/2.0/guidelines-provenance.htm>):

- **baseURL** - the baseURL of the originating repository from which the metadata record was

harvested.

- **identifier** - the unique identifier of the item in the originating repository from which the metadata record was disseminated.
- **timestamp** - the timestamp of the metadata record disseminated by the originating repository.
- **metadataNamespace** - the XML namespace URI of the metadata format of the record harvested from the originating repository.
- **repositoryId** - optional; structured as registryName: repositoryID, using the following registry name's controlled vocabulary: [opendoar](#), [re3data](#), [FAIRSharing](#), [doaj](#), and [dris](#); e.g., dris:98765; the repositoryID should not be preceded by zeros.
- **repositoryName** - optional; human-readable name of the repository.
- **harvestDate** - optional; the responseDate of the OAI-PMH response that resulted in the record being harvested from the originating repository.
- **altered** - optional; a boolean value which must be true if the harvested record was altered before being aggregated and further disseminated.
- **originDescription** - optional; a set of nested originDescription blocks indicates a sequence of harvesting and aggregation steps.

Appendix B: EEN resource product metadata profile (version 4.1, February 2021)

The EEN Resource Catalogue adopted the [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#), today implemented by the many data repository platforms (DSpace, Dataverse, InvenioRDM, Eprints), and widely adopted in Europe and worldwide (~1000 data sources). The specific properties and usage of the [DataCite Application Profile](#) are listed in this section.

The following requirement levels for the metadata properties are used:

- **Mandatory (M)** The property must always be present in the metadata. An empty value for the property is not allowed.
- **Mandatory if Applicable (MA)** When the property value can be obtained, it must be present in the metadata.
- **Recommended (R)** The use of the property is recommended.
- **Optional (O)** It is not important whether the property is used or not, but if used it may provide complementary information about the resource.

This documentation uses the following namespace abbreviations:

- dc: <http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/>
- dcterms: <http://purl.org/dc/terms/>
- datacite: <http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4>
- oaire: <http://namespace.openaire.eu/schema/oaire/>

OpenAIRE-Field	Metadata Element	Refinement by Vocabulary	FAIR
Title (M)	datacite:title	title type	
Creator (MA)	datacite:creator	name type	RDA-I3-01M
Contributor (MA)	datacite:contributor	name type contributor type	
Funding Reference (MA)	oaire:fundingReference	funderIdentifier type	
Alternate Identifier (R)	datacite:alternateIdentifier	alternateIdentifier type	RDA-F1-02M

Related Identifier (R)	datacite:relatedIdentifier	relatedIdentifier type relation type resourcetype general	RDA-I3-01M RDA-I3-02M RDA-I3-03M RDA-I3-04M
Embargo Period Date (MA)	datacite:date	date type	
Language (MA)	dc:language	IETF BCP 47, ISO 639-3	
Publisher (MA)	dc:publisher		
Publication Date (M)	datacite:date	date type	
Resource Type (M)	oaire:resourceType	COAR Resource Type Vocabulary	
Description (MA)	dc:description		
Format (R)	dc:format		RDA-I1-01D
Resource Identifier (M)	datacite:identifier	identifier type	RDA-F1-01M RDA-F1-02M RDA-A1.1-01D
Access Rights (M)	datacite:rights	COAR Access Right Vocabulary	RDA-A1-01M
Source (R)	dc:source		

Subject (MA)	datacite:subject		RDA-I1-01M
License Condition (R)	oaire:licenseCondition		RDA-R1.1-01M RDA-R1.1-02M RDA-R1.1-03M
Coverage (R)	dc:coverage		
Size (O)	datacite:size		
Geo Location (O)	datacite:geoLocation		
Resource Version (R)	oaire:version	COAR Version Vocabulary	
File Location (MA)	oaire:file	COAR Access Right Vocabulary	RDA-F3-01M
Citation Title (R)	oaire:citationTitle		
Citation Volume (R)	oaire:citationVolume		
Citation Issue (R)	oaire:citationIssue		
Citation Start Page (R)	oaire:citationStartPage		
Citation End Page (R)	oaire:citationEndPage		
Citation Edition (R)	oaire:citationEdition		

Citation Conference Place (R)	oaire:citationConferencePlace		
Citation Conference Date (R)	oaire:citationConferenceDate		
Audience (O)	dcterms:audience		

The application profile is implemented in XML Schema. [The files](#) for the application profile and [sample XML files](#) are part of these Guidelines and also available on the [GitHub repository](#). In the XML metadata documents the schema must be declared as follows:

```
<oaire:resource xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xmlns:dc="http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/"
  xmlns:dcterms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/"
  xmlns:datacite="http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4"
  xmlns:oaire="http://namespace.openaire.eu/schema/oaire/"
  xsi:schemaLocation="http://namespace.openaire.eu/schema/oaire/
  https://www.openaire.eu/schema/repo-lit/4.0/openaire.xsd">
```

Appendix C: User Guide for Nodes (Version 0.1.5 - 29/7/2025)

This guide provides step-by-step instructions for EOSC Node staff to register a Node or catalogue in the EEN. It walks users through the Contributor Dashboard wizard, which can be accessed via the EOSC EU Node's User Space.

1. Node Enrolment

1.1 Manage Contributors

The screenshot displays the 'Manage Contributors' interface. On the left, a sidebar lists navigation options, with 'Manage Contributors' selected (1). The main area shows a list of draft contributor organisations. At the top, there is a filter bar (2) with 'Draft' selected. The list contains five entries, with 'Test Node 23/7/2025 No 3' highlighted in blue (3). The entry 'Test Node 23/7/2025 No 2' has three vertical lines (4) indicating a menu option.

- Once the EOSC EU Node Onboarding Team creates your Node draft entry, you will receive an email to finish enrolment. To do so, as a first step, you may log in to your **User Space** and navigate to the **Manage Contributors** page - (1)
- To facilitate the detection of the draft Node entry, you may use the filters on the top of the page - (2)
- To resume and complete the Node enrolment procedure, you may either click on the draft Node's name, or on the three vertical lines and select the **Resume Application** option - (3), (4)

1.2 Basic Information

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Node' wizard interface. The left pane contains a navigation menu with steps 1-6. Step 1, 'Basic Information', is selected and has a progress bar at 23% completion. The right pane shows the form for step 1 with fields for Name, Abbreviation, Website, Legal Entity, and Node Type. Red circles with numbers 1-11 highlight key UI elements: 1 (step indicator), 2 (step title), 3 (progress bar), 4 (Name field), 5 (Abbreviation field), 6 (Website field), 7 (Legal Entity radio buttons), 8 (Node Type dropdown), 9 (Next button), 10 (Cancel and Exit button), and 11 (Update Node button).

- After entering the Node enrolment wizard, you will be presented with a two-pane view. The various steps of the wizard are enumerated on the left pane. Each step has a number of mandatory fields marked with a circle next to its title. The total percentage of mandatory fields completed for the entire wizard is also indicated at the bottom of the left pane - (1), (2), (3)
- In the first step of the wizard, you will be asked to fill-in some **Basic Information** for your Node, including its **Name**, **Abbreviation** and **Website** address (name and abbreviation follow the agreed federation node naming conventions) - (4), (5), (6)
- You must also indicate whether the Node is a **Legal Entity** or not - (7)
- Finally, you may also optionally select the type of the Node (i.e., one of **EU Wide**, **National**, **Regional**, or **Thematic**) - (8)
- To proceed to the next step of the wizard, click on the **Next** button - (9)
- You may cancel the process and exit at any time without saving by clicking on the **Cancel and Exit** button - (10)
- To update the draft application for your Node enrolment and exit the wizard without submitting it, click on the **Update Node** button - (11)

1.3 Profile

- At the **Profile** step of the wizard, you must provide a short **Description** of your Node organization (i.e., not more than 1000 characters).
- You must also provide a URL pointing to the **Logo** of your Node organization. The logo can be of any image type (e.g., PNG, JPEG) - (1), (2)

1.4 Location

- At the **Location** step of the wizard, you must provide the location information of your Node organization. Specifically, you must provide the **Address**, **Postal Code**, **City**, and **Country** of your organization - (1), (2), (3), (4)
- Optionally, you may provide the **Region** of your Node Organisation - (5)

Edit Node

Fields with (*) are mandatory.
Important: All information must be provided in the English language.
Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic information *
- Profile *
- Location *** (3)
- Contact *
- Users
- Overview

2/4 required steps completed
46%

Cancel and Exit Update Node

Address *
Street name and number of the Contributor's premises.
Up to 50 characters

Postal Code *
The postal code of the Contributor's premises' address.

City *
The city where the Contributor's premises are located.

Region
The region where the Contributor's premises are located.
Up to 20 characters

Country *
The country where the Contributor's premises are located.

Previous Next >

1.5 Contact

Edit Node

Fields with (*) are mandatory.
Important: All information must be provided in the English language.
Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic information *
- Profile *
- Location *
- Contact *** (4)
- Users
- Overview

3/4 required steps completed
76%

Cancel and Exit Update Node

Main Contact *

First Name *
The first name of the Contributor's main contact person.
Up to 50 characters

Last Name *
The last name of the Contributor's main contact person.
Up to 50 characters

Email *
The email of the Contributor's main contact person.

Phone Country Code
The phone country code

Phone
The phone of the Contributor's main contact person.
Up to 10 characters

Position
The organisational position of the Contributor's main contact person.
Up to 50 characters

Previous Next >

- Next, at the **Contact** step of the wizard, you must provide the details of the Node's main contact person, namely the Node Coordinator. Specifically, you must provide his/her **First Name**, **Last Name** and **Email**. Please note that the main contact must be a registered EOSC EU Node user - (1), (2), (3)

- Optionally, you may provide his/her **Phone** number and organizational **Position** - (4), (5)

1.6 Users

The screenshot shows the 'Edit Node' wizard interface. On the left, a sidebar lists various services and general settings, with 'Users' highlighted as the current step. The main area is titled 'Users' and contains three input fields for administrator details: 'First name' (Diana), 'Last name' (Brown), and 'Email' (brown_03@example.domain). Red circles with numbers 1, 2, and 3 are overlaid on these fields. At the bottom, a progress bar shows '4/4 required steps completed' and '100%'. Buttons for 'Cancel and Exit', 'Update Node', 'Previous', and 'Next' are visible.

- At the **Users** step of the wizard, you are presented with non-editable fields containing the details of the administrator user of the Node under enrolment, which was provided during the initial creation of the draft application by the EOSC EU Node Onboarding Team. Specifically, you can view his/her **First Name**, **Last Name** and **Email**. The administrator user must have an active account on the EOSC EU Node - (1), (2), (3)

1.7 Overview

- Finally, at the **Overview** step of the wizard, you have the opportunity to go through all the details that you have provided for your Node organisation
- To edit a field before submitting, you may either click on the corresponding step title at the left pane of the wizard, or at the **Edit** button above each category - (1), (2)
- To submit the application for review, click on the Publish Node button. You will be presented with a confirmation modal. Upon successful submission the Node's application will appear as having the 'Pending' status in the **Manage Contributors** tab in your **User Space**. Once the application is validated and accepted by the EOSC EU Node Onboarding Team and the European Commission, your Node organisation will appear as 'Enroled' in the **Manage Contributors** tab in your **User Space** - (3)

2. Onboard a Data Source from a Node

2.1 Node Dashboard

- When you submit your Node enrolment application for review, you will be able to visit your **Node Dashboard** page by clicking on the arrow next to your username while in the **User Space** and selecting your Node. Please note that if your Node enrolment application is under review by the EOSC EU Node Onboarding Team and the European Commission, the status of your node will appear as ‘Pending’. From there, you may start onboarding resources even while your enrolment application is still pending. Currently, only **Data Source** onboarding is supported for Nodes - (1)
- To onboard a **Data Source**, visit the **Resources** tab in the **Node Dashboard**, click on the **Add Resource** button and then on the **Data Source** button. Doing so will initiate the **Create a Data Source** wizard - (2), (3)

2.2 Basic Metadata

- In the first page of the **Create a Data Source** wizard, you will be presented with a two-pane view. The various steps of the wizard are enumerated in the left panel. Each step has several mandatory fields marked with a circle next to its title. The total percentage of mandatory fields completed for the entire wizard is also indicated at the bottom of the left pane - (1), (2)
- During the first step of the wizard, you will be asked to fill-in some **Basic Information** for your Data Source, including its **Name**, **Abbreviation**, and **Website** address - (3), (4), (5)
- You may cancel the process and exit at any time without saving by clicking on the **Cancel and Exit** button - (6)
- To update the draft application for your Data Source onboarding and exit the wizard without submitting it, click on the **Save Data Source as Draft** button - (7)

- To proceed to the next step of the wizard, click on the **Next** button - (8)

2.3 Marketing

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Data Source' wizard in the 'Marketing' step. The progress bar indicates 12% completion (1/7 steps). The 'Marketing' step is highlighted. The form contains the following fields and elements:

- Description** (1): A large text area for a high-level, non-technical description. A red circle (1) is placed over the text area. A red error message below it states: "The 'Description' field is required. Up to 1000 characters".
- Tagline** (4): A text area for a short catchphrase. A red circle (4) is placed over the text area.
- Logo** (5): A text area for a link to the logo, with a placeholder "use http:// or https://". A red circle (5) is placed over the text area.
- Language** (2): A dropdown menu currently set to "English". A red circle (2) is placed over the dropdown. An "Add Language +" button (3) is located to the right of the dropdown.

At the bottom of the form, there are buttons for "Cancel and Exit", "Save Data Source as Draft", "Previous", and "Next" (8).

- In the **Marketing** step of the wizard, you must provide a non-technical **Description** and the **Language** of your Data Source - (1), (2)
- You can add more languages by clicking the **Add Language** button - (3)
- You may also optionally provide a **Tagline** (i.e., a short catchphrase describing the Data Source) and a URL pointing to the **Logo** of the Data Source. The logo can be of any image type (e.g., PNG, JPEG) - (4), (5)

2.4 Classification

- Next, in the **Classification** part of the wizard, you must select the **Scientific Domain** and **Subdomain** of your Data Source. In case no scientific domain and/or subdomain are applicable to your Data Source, you can select the 'Other' or 'Generic' value. You may add more domains by clicking on the **Add Scientific Categorization** button - (1), (2), (3)
- You can optionally add one more **Tags** (i.e., related keywords) to the Data Source - (4), (5)

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Fields with (*) are mandatory.
Important: All information must be provided in the English language.
Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

Basic * ✓

Marketing * ✓

Classification * 1*

Location

Contact * 3*

Maturity

Management * 2*

Data Source Information * 3*

Data Source Metadata * 10*

Acknowledgement and Acceptance

Overview

2/7 required steps completed
20%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft

Scientific Categorisation *

Scientific Domain *
The scientific discipline of the Data Source.

Generic

Scientific Subdomain *
The scientific sub-discipline of the Data Source.

The "Scientific Subdomain" field is required

Add Scientific Categorisation +

Tags
Keywords associated to the Data Source.

Add Tags +

Previous Next >

2.5 Location

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Fields with (*) are mandatory.
Important: All information must be provided in the English language.
Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

Basic * ✓

Marketing * ✓

Classification * ✓

Location 4

Contact * 3*

Maturity

Management * 2*

Data Source Information * 3*

Data Source Metadata * 10*

Acknowledgement and Acceptance

Overview

3/7 required steps completed
25%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft

Geographic Locations
List of geographic locations covered by the Data Source.

Add Geographic Location +

Previous Next >

- Next, you may optionally select one or more **Geographic Locations** that are covered by the Data Source - (1), (2)

2.6 Contact

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Data Source' wizard in the EOSC EU Node interface. The current step is 'Contact', which is highlighted in blue. The form contains the following fields:

- 1** First Name * (Up to 20 characters)
- 2** Last Name * (Up to 20 characters)
- 3** Email *
- 4** Phone (Phone Country Code and Phone number, up to 10 characters)
- 5** Organisation (Up to 50 characters)
- 6** Position (Up to 20 characters)

At the bottom of the form, there is a progress bar indicating '3/7 required steps completed' (25%) and buttons for 'Cancel and Exit', 'Save Data Source as Draft', 'Previous', and 'Next'.

- In the **Contact** step of the wizard, you must provide details of the main contact person for the Data Source. Please note that the main contact should be a registered EOSC EU Node user
- Specifically, you must provide the main contact's **First Name**, **Last Name**, and **Email** - (1), (2), (3)
- You can optionally provide his/her **Phone**, **Organisation** and **Position** in that organization - (4), (5), (6)

2.7 Maturity

- Next, in the **Maturity** step, you can optionally select one or **Certifications** that were obtained for the Data Source that is being onboarded - (1), (2)

2.8 Management (I/II)

- In the **Management** step of the wizard, you will be asked to provide the **Helpdesk Email** and **Security Contact Email** for your Data Source - (1), (2)
- You can also optionally provide the URL of the Data Source's **Helpdesk Page**, a URL pointing to the **User Manual** of the Data Source, a URL pointing to the **Terms of Use** of the Data Source, a URL pointing to the **Privacy Policy** of the Data Source and more (see the next page) - (3), (4),

(5), (6)

2.9 Management (II/II)

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Data Source' wizard in the 'Management' step. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Overview, Resources, Profile, Profile History, QUICKLINKS, Helpdesk, and EOSC EU Node. The main content area displays a progress bar at the bottom indicating '4/7 required steps completed' (37%). The 'Management' step is highlighted with a red circle and the number '1'. Below it, the 'Data Source Information' step is highlighted with a red circle and the number '2'. The right side of the wizard contains several text input fields with labels and instructions:

- Helpdesk Email:** The "Helpdesk Email" field is required.
- Security Contact Email:** The email of the Data Source's security contact. The "Security Contact Email" field is required.
- User Manual:** Link to the Data Source's user manual or documentation. (use http:// or https://)
- Terms of Use:** The page containing the Terms of User for the Data Source. (use http:// or https://)
- Privacy Policy:** Link to the privacy policy of the Data Source. (use http:// or https://)
- Access Policy (Acceptable Use Policy):** Link to the acceptable use policy of the Data Source. (use http:// or https://)
- User Access Policy (URL):** Link to the user access policy of the Data Source. (use http:// or https://)

At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Cancel and Exit', 'Save Data Source as Draft', 'Previous', and 'Next >'.

- After scrolling down the page in the **Management** step of the wizard, you will be able to optionally provide URLs for the **Acceptable Use Policy** and **User Access Policy** of the Data Source - (1), (2)

2.10 Data Source Information

- Next, in the **Data Source Information** step of the wizard, you must provide the Data Source Type (i.e., **Software Repositories**, **Publications** or **Data**) and select one or more Persistent Identity Systems for the Data Source - (1), (2), (3), (4)
- You can also optionally provide the **Submission Policy URL**, the **Preservation Policy URL** of the Data Source, and indicate whether **Version Control** will be applied to the Data Source - (5), (6), (7)

Create a Data Source

Fields with (*) are mandatory. Important: All information must be provided in the English language. Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic *
- Marketing *
- Classification *
- Location
- Contact *
- Maturity
- Management *
- Data Source Information *** (3*)
- Data Source Metadata * (10*)
- Acknowledgement and Acceptance
- Overview

5/7 required steps completed
45%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft Previous Next >

Datasource Type * 1

Submission Policy URL
Link to the submission policy of the Data Source.
use http:// or https:// 5

Preservation Policy URL
Link to the preservation policy of the Data Source.
use http:// or https:// 6

Version Control
Whether version control will be applied for the Data Source or not.
 No Yes 7

Persistent Identity Systems *

Persistent Identity Entity Type * 2

Persistent Identity Entity Type Schemes * 3

Add Persistent Identity System + 4

2.11 Data Source Metadata (I/IV)

Create a Data Source

Fields with (*) are mandatory. Important: All information must be provided in the English language. Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic *
- Marketing *
- Classification *
- Location
- Contact *
- Maturity
- Management *
- Data Source Information *
- Data Source Metadata *** (10*)
- Acknowledgement and Acceptance
- Overview

6/7 required steps completed
86%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft Previous Next >

Jurisdiction * 1
The jurisdiction of the Data Source.

Datasource Classification * 2
The data classification for the Data Source.

Thematic * 3
Whether the Data Source is thematic, or not.
 No Yes

Research Product Access Policy 4
The access policy of the research product related to the Data Source.
Add Research Product Access Policy + 5

Research Product Metadata Licensing *

Research Product Metadata License Name * 6
The license name of the research product metadata related to the Data Source.

Research Product Metadata License URL * 7
The license URL of the research product metadata related to the Data Source.
use http:// or https://

- In the **Data Source Metadata** step of the wizard, you must initially select the **Jurisdiction** (pool of users the data source is intended to serve) of the Data Source (i.e., either **Global**, **Institution**, **National**, or **Regional** aka multiple countries) and the **Data Source Classification** (i.e., one of **Research Product Data Source**, **Scientific Database**, or **Service Catalogue**). Please note that, depending on what you select in this step, the mandatory fields in this step

of the wizard change: while there are 10 mandatory fields for research product Data Sources and scientific databases, there are only 4 for service catalogues - (1), (2)

- You must also select whether the Data Source that is being onboarded is **Thematic** or not (i.e., a data source that is organized around a specific theme, subject, or domain of interest, rather than being general-purpose or broadly scoped) - (3)
- You can optionally select one or more **Access Policies** for the research product related to the Data Source that is being onboarded - (4), (5)
- If the Data Source is either a **Research Product Data Source** or a **Scientific Database** (based on what was selected in the **Data Source Classification** field), you must provide details for the related **Research Product Metadata Licensing** (i.e., name and URL) - (6), (7)

2.12 Data Source Metadata (II/IV)

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Data Source' wizard in the EOSC EU Node interface. The 'Data Source Metadata' step is the current focus, indicated by a blue highlight and a progress bar showing 56% completion (9/17 required steps). The form includes the following fields and options:

- Base URL ***: A text input field with a placeholder 'use http:// or https://'. Marked with a red circle (1).
- Research Product Metadata Access Policies**: A section for adding policies, with a red circle (2) over the 'Add Research Product Metadata Access Policy +' button.
- Harvestable**: A section with radio buttons for 'No' and 'Yes'. Marked with a red circle (4).
- Protocol**: A dropdown menu. Marked with a red circle (3).
- OAI Sets**: A section for adding OAI sets, with a red circle (5) over the 'Add OAI Set +' button.
- Format**: A dropdown menu. Marked with a red circle (7).
- Compatibility ***: A section for selecting compatibility options.

- Scrolling down the **Data Source Metadata** step of the wizard, you will be asked to provide the **Base URL** of the Data Source - (1)
- You may also optionally provide one or more **Access Policies** for the related research product metadata, indicate whether the Data Source is harvestable by other entities or not, select the **Protocol** of the Data Source (i.e., **FTP**, **OAI**, **Rest API** or **Other**), add one or more **OAI Sets** and select the **Format** of the Data Source - (2), (3), (4), (5), (6), (7)

2.13 Data Source Metadata (III/IV)

The screenshot shows the 'Create a Data Source' wizard. The left sidebar contains navigation options like 'Overview', 'Resources', 'Profile', and 'Data Source Metadata'. The main content area has several form fields: 'Format', 'Compatibility' (with a red circle 1), 'Compliance to OpenAIRE Guidelines' (with a red circle 2), 'Repository Identifier' (with a red circle 3), and 'Repository Identifier Type' (with a red circle 4). There is also an 'Alternative Identifiers' section at the bottom. The progress bar at the bottom indicates 6/7 required steps completed (58%).

- If the Data Source is either a **Research Product Data Source** (based on what was selected in the **Data Source Classification** field), scrolling further down the **Data Source Metadata** step of the wizard, you must ensure **Compatibility** of the Data Source to the [OpenAIRE guidelines 4.0](#) - (1), (2)
- You must also provide the **Repository Identifier** (and its type) of the Data Source. The repository must be already registered in one of the following global registries: [OpenDOAR](#) (for Literature Repositories), [Re3Data](#) (for Data Repositories) or [FAIRsharing](#) (for Data and Literature Repositories). The repository must also be compatible with the [OpenAIRE Guidelines 4.0](#) - (3), (4)

2.14 Data Source Metadata (IV/IV)

- Finally, scrolling at the bottom of the **Data Source Metadata** step of the wizard, you can optionally provide one or more alternative repository identifiers and their type - (1), (2), (3)

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Fields with (*) are mandatory. Important: All information must be provided in the English language. Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic *
- Marketing *
- Classification *
- 4 Location
- Contact *
- 6 Maturity
- Management *
- Data Source Information *
- 9 **Data Source Metadata *** 10*
- 10 Acknowledgement and Acceptance
- 11 Overview

6/7 required steps completed 58%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft Previous Next >

Guidelines *OpenAIRE for institutional and Thematic Repositories (OpenAIRE 4.0).

No Yes

Repository Identifier *

The repository identifier of the Data Source.

Repository Identifier Type *

The repository identifier type (e.g. opendoar, r3data, fairsharing) of the Data Source.

Alternative Identifiers

Alternative Identifier

This is Alternative Identifier

Alternative Identifier Type

This is Alternative Identifier Type

Add Alternative Identifier +

2.15 Acknowledgment and Acceptance

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Fields with (*) are mandatory. Important: All information must be provided in the English language. Non-English submissions will result in rejection.

- Basic *
- Marketing *
- Classification *
- 4 Location
- Contact *
- 6 Maturity
- Management *
- Data Source Information *
- Data Source Metadata *
- 10 **Acknowledgement and Acceptance**
- 11 Overview

7/7 required steps completed 100%

Cancel and Exit Save Data Source as Draft Previous Next >

Acknowledgement and Acceptance *

I confirm that I accept the following conditions:

- Information submitted in the present form will be automatically stored in the EOSC EU Node Catalogue services.
- Selected information from the present form will be automatically presented in the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub upon successful Onboarding.
- Registered service endpoints will be automatically monitored by the EOSC EU Node Monitoring Service for basic service uptime checks.
- The registered security contact point may be contacted by the EOSC EU Node Security Team in case of security incident.

- In the **Acknowledgment and Acceptance** step of the wizard, you must provide your consent to the following:
- Information submitted in the present form to be automatically stored in the EOSC EU Node Catalogue services - (1)
- Selected information from the present form to be automatically presented in the EOSC EU Node

Resource Hub upon successful Onboarding - (2)

- Registered service endpoints to be automatically monitored by the EOSC EU Node Monitoring Service for basic service uptime checks - (3)
- The registered security contact point to be contacted by the EOSC EU Node Security Team in case of security incident - (4)

2.16 Overview

The screenshot displays the 'Create a Data Source' wizard. The left sidebar shows the 'Overview' step selected. The central pane lists 11 steps, with 'Basic' circled in red and labeled '1'. The right-hand form area shows the 'Basic' section circled in red and labeled '2', and the 'Contact' section circled in red and labeled '3'. The form includes fields for Name, Abbreviation, Webpage, Description, Tagline, Logo, Languages, Scientific Domain, Scientific Subdomain, Location, and Main Contact. At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Cancel and Exit', 'Save Data Source as Draft', 'Previous', and 'Publish Data Source'. A progress indicator shows '7/7 required steps completed' and '100%'.

- Finally, at the **Overview** step of the wizard, you have the opportunity to go through all the details that you have provided for the Data Source to be onboarded
- To edit a field before submitting, you may either click on the corresponding step title in the left pane of the wizard, or on the **Edit** button above each category - (1), (2)
- To submit the application for review, click on the **Publish Data Source** button. You will be presented with a confirmation modal. Upon successful submission the Data Source's application will appear as having the 'Pending' status in the **Resources** tab in your **Node Dashboard**. Once the application is validated and accepted by the EOSC EU Node Onboarding Team and the European Commission, your Data Source will appear as 'Onboarded' in the **Resources** tab in your **Node Dashboard** - (3)